

A STUDY EXAMINING CHANGING LIFESTYLE AND LEARNING PROCESS OF YOUNG GENERATION IN THANE CITY DUE TO COVID 19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract:

In the year 2020, entire world is suffering from COVID 19 pandemic. World has a history of some of the major pandemics that have occurred over the time. COVID- 19 was first reported in Wuhan, China, and subsequently spread worldwide. Currently, people all over the world have been affected by corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which is the fifth pandemic after the 1918 flu pandemic. India reported the first confirmed case of the corona virus infection on 30 January 2020 in the state of Kerala. As a preventive and safety measure against the COVID 19 Pandemic, honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modiji has announced nationwide lockdown on 24th March 2020 for 21 days in our country which was extended up to May 2020. This lockdown affects different population segments of the country like industrial workers, farmers, businessman, home servants, doctors, students etc. Young generation especially students are experiencing this situation may be for the first time in their life which affects their lifestyle, learning process, behavior etc. This COVID 19 pandemic affects the young generation positively as well as negatively.

So this paper tries to study influence of COVID -19 Pandemic on young generation in Thane city examining their lifestyle, study pattern and upgrading technical knowledge during this lockdown period.

Key words: *COVID 19 Pandemic, lock down, young generation, lifestyle, learning process etc.*

Introduction:

The entire world was already suffering from economic slowdown from the year 2019 which is again badly affected by COVID 19 Pandemic in the year 2020. Before this situation also the world was suffered from pandemics like Great Plague of London 1665, Cholera Pandemic 1817-1923, Russian Flu 1889-1890, Asian Flu 1957-1958, Swine Flu 2009-10, SARS and MERS etc. which reduced human capital on a larger scale. The corona virus transmitted in many countries in the world from China from that USA is the major sufferer of this corona virus infection. The corona virus was officially named severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses based on phylogenetic analysis. This is communicable virus which rapidly transmits from one person to another. As a safety and preventive measures government of many countries declared lockdown and curfew. In India the first patient of COVID 19 was found in January 2020. By mid-March, Corona patients were rapidly growing in India. Considering the seriousness of this situation, honorable Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced 1st Lock down in India on 24th March 2020. Even after the first lockdown, the situation was getting out of control. However, government announced another phase of lockdown till 31st May 2020.

This lockdown affected various sectors of our economy which is going to affect again our economic growth and development. Due to COVID 19 pandemic and increasing lockdown phases people were suffering from different

problems. Like the other segments of population, the young generation also influenced by this situation. Due to COVID 19 pandemic the state governments across the country temporarily started shutting down schools and colleges. As per the present situation, there is an uncertainty when schools and colleges will reopen. So, in this challenging period number of changes was observed among young generation. This research paper tried to study changes in lifestyle and changes in learning process of these students.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study lifestyle of students in lockdown period during COVID 19 pandemic.
2. To review influence of lockdown period on students learning process.
3. To examine influence of technology on students learning process in this lockdown period.

Research Methodology:

This paper is based on Primary as well as secondary data. Primary information was collected randomly from 200 students staying in Thane City of Maharashtra through online questionnaire. For better analysis, age group between 15 to 25 were selected for the survey. Secondary data collected from sources like various reports of the government, newspapers, articles, different websites etc.

Brief information about young generation:

Younger generations are considered as the backbone of every country's future. With the changing times, many changes were observed in this generation as well. Comparing this generation with the previous generation, it can be seen that the attitude of this generation towards way of life has changed radically. Adapting to technology, learning and assimilating new things is instantaneous for this generation. Giving quick response to anything is also a feature of this generation. This is probably the first time this kind of pandemic and lockdown situation has happened to this young generation. Number of changes has been observed among young adults during this lockdown period. Their learning method, wake up and sleeping time, helping in domestic work, developing hobbies, spending more time with family than friends, watching various motivational videos, learning new study material, participating in many online events etc. were examined in this lockdown period.

Findings of the study:

1. Related with their lifestyle, it is observed that there has been drastic change in their wake up and sleeping time. As compared to normal times they prefer to sleep more for 2 to 3 hours.
2. Apart from the study, young generation spend their time in helping their parents in domestic work, playing indoor games, developing their hobbies, social work, conservation of the environment etc. which created positive energy into them.
3. Many young adults became health conscious during this lockdown period by doing yoga, meditation, stretching exercise etc. which help them to maintain good health during this pandemic period. According to data collected through survey 74% of sample doing exercise. Maximum samples preferred 30 minutes to 1 hour duration for the exercise.

4. It is observed that in this lockdown period young adult experiencing changes in their eating habits, changes in their behavior and thinking. They understand the value of their life and they observed changes in their attitude towards the society.
5. Even if they have learned many new things during this lockdown period, majority of samples i.e., 43% said that they did not enjoyed their lifestyle in this lockdown period.

6. It is examined that majority of adolescent and young adults were not able to concentrate on their studies during this lockdown period. Most of them i.e., 51% were doing a study which is less than 1 hour. It is shown in following diagram.

7. It is also observed that in this pandemic period the learning method of young adults have been changed. Majority from them i.e., 87% of students took the help of technology for their study. From the various online platforms maximum from them are using online apps like Zoom, Google Meet etc. So, it is responded by them is that this lockdown period increased their technical knowledge.
8. Apart from their syllabus they spent time on watching motivational videos, Spiritual videos and videos related with social issues. They had participated in many webinars, online competitions; many of them have completed various short term online course etc.
9. However, it is observed that though adolescent and young adults used technology to attend various lectures, they are not able to concentrate always on that. They can be able to attend the online lecture which is less than 1 hour or maximum of 1 to 2 hours. It is also observed that the concentration capacity of boys was less than girl students.

10. It is examined that this lockdown period has increased use of technology by young adults. However, it is adversely affecting their health also. After attending online lectures these students were suffered from headache, irritation of eyes, effect on hearing capacity, spinal problem etc. Especially girl students were major sufferer.
11. Though it is the era of technology most of the students preferred offline method that is classroom teaching for lectures and traditional method for examinations in their future.

It is shown in following diagram.

Suggestions:

1. It has been suggested that while conducting online lectures for young adults, educational or any other institute must limit the duration of lecture. More the duration, lesser the concentration of students. So there has been a maximum limit on hours of lectures.
2. It is suggested that students have to take care of their health while attending online lectures and educational institutes or other institutes also consider students health while designing online lectures.
3. It is suggested to students that to come back to their earlier wake up and sleeping times because irregular times can affect their health.
4. It is suggested to students that be familiar and adapt online mode because now in this situation of pandemic it is very difficult to engage regular offline lectures. May be in future number of educational institutes can adopt online pattern more.

Conclusion:

It can be concluded that in any situation young generation of our country never stop learning. In this COVID 19 pandemic period, the lifestyle of many adolescent and young adults has changed but they preferred their earlier lifestyle more. Many of them exercise regularly in this period which has positive impact on their mind and body. They adopted new technology; learn many new things but this technology has negative impact also on their health. Sometimes due to more duration of online lectures, they are not able to concentrate properly. So, it suggested to educational institutes and public policy makers to frame a proper policy for online lectures. The length of online lectures should not be out of students' capacity and the lectures must be interesting by using more e-content. However, it is concluded that this pandemic period has positive as well as some negative influence on young generation of our country.

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